

Renyi Entropy and its Link with Fixed Length Vectors

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 28, 2025

In (1), a Renyi entropy based scheme is introduced to show that given a qubit (quantum mechanical) state: $I + \sum_{i=1,2,3} r_i s_i$, where r_i is a number and s_i the i th Pauli matrix, one may map this into $2^2 \cdot 2 = 8$ probability numbers q_j ($j=1,8$) such that $\sum_j q_j = 1$. Here q_j may be both positive and negative. The authors introduce Renyi entropy: $1/(q-1) \ln_{\text{base } 2} \{ \sum_{j=1}^8 q_j^{\text{power } 2} \}$ and show that for $k=1$, Renyi entropy is extremized for $\sum_{i=1,2,3} r_i = 1$. In other words, (1) starts with the notion of 8 q_i points and shows that qubit quantum states which extremize power 2 Renyi entropy represent all normalized (r_1, r_2, r_3) values.

We suggest here that Renyi entropy with power=2 is essentially a modulus based entropy which treats any q_i set with the same modulus as having the same entropy. As a result, even in the case of 3-vectors in space (which are not quantum mechanical), one may map (x,y,z) into a power 2 Renyi entropy with log base r to show that any x,y,z vector with the same magnitude extremizes the entropy. In other words, there is a 1-1 mapping between constant magnitudes in some space and Renyi entropy with power=2, we argue. As a result, we suggest that the Renyi power 2 entropy is equivalent to the notion of all vectors of the same magnitude being on the same footing in terms of Renyi entropy, even if one does not consider 3 spatial dimensions.

Scheme of (1)

In (1), a Renyi entropy scheme is applied to a qubit defined by:

$$I + \sum_{i=1,2,3} r_i s_i, \quad \text{where } r_i \text{ is a number and } s_i \text{ the } i\text{th Pauli matrix} \quad ((1))$$

Here I is the 2×2 identity matrix.

The idea seems to be that each Pauli matrix is linked with two choices (spin up and down) and so there are $2^2 \cdot 2 = 8$ points or probabilities to deal with. It is suggested then that:

$$\sum q_i = 1 \quad \text{where } i=1 \text{ to } 8 \quad \text{and } q_i \text{ may be positive or negative} \quad ((2))$$

The idea is then to introduce Renyi entropy with \ln base 2:

$$1/(q-1) \ln_{\text{base } 2} \{ \sum_{j=1}^8 q_j^{\text{power } 2} \} \quad \text{as well for other powers} \quad ((3))$$

The power 2 case is particularly examined and the q_i set which extremizes Renyi entropy (gives it a value of 2) is one for which:

Magnitude $q = 2$ or $q \cdot q = 1/4$ ((4))

If one writes: $q_i = \frac{1}{8}(1 + c_i)$, then: $\sum_{i=1,8} c_i = 0$ ((5a)) and $1/64 (8 + \sum c_i c_i) = 1/4$ or

$\sum c_i c_i = 8$ ((5b)) Any c_i set of 8 satisfying ((5a)) and ((5b)) suffice.

A simple solution is $\frac{1}{8}(1+c_i) = \frac{1}{8}\{2,0,2,0,2,0,2,0\}$. A set given in (1) is: $\frac{1}{8}(1+\sqrt{3}, 1+1/\sqrt{3}, 1-1/\sqrt{3}, 1+1/\sqrt{3}, 1-1/\sqrt{3}, 1-\sqrt{3}, 1-\sqrt{3}, 1-\sqrt{3})$.

One may even use $c_1=a, c_2=b, c_3=c, c_4$ to $c_8=0$ such that $a+b+c=0$ and $aa+bb+cc=8$.

In this case, $(a+b+c)(a+b+c)=0$ so $8+2ab+2ac+2bc=0$ or $-4 = ab+ac+bc$ and $-4 = -(b+c)(b+c) + bc$. If $a>0$, one may choose a negative value for b such that $aa+bb+cc=8$ is not violated and solve a quadratic for c . Then $a+b+c=0$ yields a . In other words, there are many choices for the q -vector which extremize entropy. The question is: What impact does extremized power 2 Renyi have on the physical qubit quantum states, i.e. on the r_1, r_2, r_3 values.

In (1), it is stated a priori that there exists a matrix A such that: $Aq = (r_1, r_2, r_3, 1)$ and this matrix is explicitly given. (1) notes that extremizes Renyi entropy in base 2 is equivalent to fixing the modulus of q , but ultimately this fixes the modulus of $r_1, r_2, r_3, 1$ and hence r_1, r_2, r_3 , namely (1) states that:

$r_1 r_1 + r_2 r_2 + r_3 r_3 = 1$ for extreme Renyi entropy ((6))

In other words, (1) uses an a priori Renyi entropy and shows that for the power 2 case it leads to all normalized (to 1) r_1, r_2, r_3 states yielding extreme entropy. This is equivalent to stating that all such normalized states carry the same weight which is statement which may be made a priori, we argue, (1), however, wishes to show that the notion of quantum mechanical states arise from entropic considerations, it seems, hence their introduction of q_i and Renyi entropy a priori.

((1)) then goes on to show that for higher powers than 2, Renyi entropy ≥ 2 .

We suggest that this model follows from the notion of Renyi entropy for power 2 is automatically linked with then notion of magnitude of a probability vector and that extremizing picks a particular magnitude value. This, we argue, may be mapped back into a set of physical vectors (quantum mechanical or not) of equal magnitude which are associated with this extremized Renyi entropy, whether or not one considers qubits or even quantum mechanics. We consider the case of vectors in 3-space in the next section.

3-Vector in Space and Renyi Entropy

A 3-vector is given by three pieces of information, x,y,z . If one considers vectors with the same magnitude, one may argue that one needs to know the dimension of space and the magnitude of the vector and then all vectors are on the same footing because of rotational invariance. This may be formalized, we argue, by introducing a Renyi entropy with power 2 which is automatically linked with the magnitude of the probability vector. The Renyi entropy, however, does not depend on how many dimensions are involved, only on the numerical value of the modulus.

Given x,y,z with a constraint of $xx+yy+zz=r$ one may use \ln base r in Renyi entropy to pick out vectors with magnitude r as the ones which extremize the entropy i.e.

$$\frac{1}{(1-2)} \ln_{\text{base } r} \{xx+yy+zz\}^{\text{power } .5} \quad ((8))$$

In principle, x,y,z are not normalized to 1, but ((8)) is a math expression which is extremized by all vectors of magnitude r . In other words, these are all placed on the same footing.

Even though x,y and z are not normalized to 1 as probabilities should be, we argue that the basic idea of the Renyi entropy with power 2 and a \ln base r automatically picks out any vector with a certain magnitude as extremizing it. We suggest that this is a key point used in (1) that is actually general and applies outside of qubits and quantum mechanics.

In other words, Renyi entropy with power 2 allows one to express an entropic equivalence for all vectors with a given magnitude. One may note that the Renyi entropy ((8)) would be the same for vectors of different dimensions as long as they had the same magnitude. Thus, the dimension of the space is not even a consideration, only the vector magnitude in the Renyi scheme.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine a scheme introduced in (1) to associate qubits with a Renyi entropy uncertainty relation such that extreme Renyi entropy, using \ln base 2 and power=2 means that one has $r_1r_1+r_2r_2+r_3r_3=1$ for weights of the Pauli matrices. We suggest that Renyi entropy with power=2 uses the magnitude of the probability vector as the argument of \ln base magnitude and so all vectors (regardless of dimension) with the same magnitude yield the same extreme Renyi entropy in such a case. Using \ln base r one may focus on an expression involving $\frac{1}{(1-2)} \ln_{\text{base } r} (xx+yy+zz)^{\text{power } .5}$. Which picks out vectors of length r has all having the same entropy. Even vectors of different dimensions with the same magnitude yield the same Renyi entropy in this case.

References

1. Brandenburger, A. and LaMura, P and Zoble, S. Renyi Entropies, Signed Probabiliteis and the Qubit 2022

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